

AN OBJECTIVE STUDY OF RESIN INJECTION MACHINES FOR RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING OF BOTH LOW COST PRODUCTS AND ADVANCES COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Until recently, Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) was used mostly for high volume, low cost composites, however, this has been changing due to new research in the area of advances composites. There now exists a visible trend toward the use of RTM medium volume production, i.e., from 1,000 to 10,000 parts.

In this study, the variables concerning the RTM process will be discussed as well as their relationship with the resin injection machine. Specific guidelines will be established to ensure that molders will select RTM machines suitable to their applications.

Keywords: Resin transfer molding, Injection machine, Process parameters.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Today, RTM is employed not only for high volume products, but in high performance markets as well.

Resin injection machines have improved significantly during the last few decades with regard to dosage, mixture and efficient injection technologies. And these machines continue to evolve rapidly according growing market demand.

Injection machines play a very important role in the quality of parts molded by resin transfer. the major criteria concerning the selection of these machines will be presented in the following sections.

2.0 PRODUCTION PARAMETERS AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP WITH THE INJECTION MACHINE

RTM production parameters and their relationship with the injection machine will be examined in this section. As a result of this examination it will be possible to evaluate the influence of the injection machine on the quality of parts produced by RTM.

The important production parameters [1] to be examined are:

1. Reinforcement
 - type of fibres
 - style of reinforcement (mat, fabric, etc.)
 - stacking sequence
 - volumetric content (vf)
2. Resin
 - chemical family (polyester, epoxy, etc.)
 - formulation (catalysts, accelerators, etc.)
 - relationship of viscosity with temperature and time
 - required proportions for catalysts and accelerators (see Table 1)
3. Molds
 - internal geometry of the cavity
 - surface finish of the cavity
 - position and number of injection ports and vents
 - thermal characteristics
4. Specific molding conditions
 - resin injection speed
 - resin injection pressure
 - resin temperature
 - use or non-use of vacuum
 - desired production rate
 - control of production parameters required
 - degree of automation required
 - ambient conditions

The above parameters are not independent of each other since the injection machine is directly related to several factors such as:

- resin preparation (metering and mixing)
- resin temperature and viscosity
- resin flow speed
- injection pressure

There is a great diversity of resins used in RTM (see Table 1) and important differences in the resin/catalyst ratios as well. For example, increased accuracy is critical for polyester resins due to their low catalyst percentages (from 0.8 to 2.5%). On the other hand, epoxies are less sensitive since the ratio is often 1:1. In all cases, it is necessary to exert a perfect control on the metering and mixing of components.

The resin must correctly impregnate the reinforcement placed in the mold. The quality of this impregnation depends mostly upon the viscosity and flow speed of the resin, upon the reinforcement and upon the desired volumetric content. Resin viscosity, which must be precisely controlled, can be minimized with uniform heating not only in the injection machine but also in the mold. A low-viscosity resin has less tendency to entrap air and to displace fibres, and realizes a much easier fibre impregnation.

Resin flow speed is also a very important parameter for the control of porosity. For example, it should not be so high as to create turbulence. Rather it should permit impregnation without displacing the fibres. The higher the volumetric content of the reinforcement, the lower the resin flow speed. In high volumetric content situations, it also becomes necessary to create a vacuum via the venting system in order to reduce porosity to a minimum, i.e., less than 1%.

3.0 SELECTION OF AN INJECTION MACHINE AS RELATED TO THE APPLICATION

In Resin Transfer Molding it is critical to have precise control of the metering, mixing and injection, three actions carried out by the injection machine. In this section the system components of the injection machine will be presented along with judicious selection criteria.

Pumping system:

Pumps play a very important role in the injection machine [2, 3]. On one hand they assure adequate dosage of the resin and catalyst and on the other they supply the flow and pressure required for injection. The type of pump to be used is largely determined by the control required for the flow and the injection pressure. Controlled injection gives a resin flow that moves at a preset speed, independent of the back pressure in the mold. This provides for smooth resin filling of the mold without risk of waviness in the molded product. The ability to modify the flow during injection is particularly important for intricate mold cavities.

Injection by controlled pressure requires a transducer in the mold or at the injection head. Controlled pressure injection offers the fastest resin filling of the mold with minimum risk of washing or overloading.

Pumps used for RTM are indicated in Table 2. Positive displacement pumps are essential to obtain precise resin and catalyst dosage and also for positive injection pressures, usually in the 10 to 3,000KPa range [4].

Metering system:

As previously stated, many types of resins are used in RTM with wide differences in resin/catalyst ratios. The metering system can be fixed or variable, however in all cases must be precise and constant.

Variable dosage systems are used when rapid resin/catalyst ratio changes are necessary, as caused by changing resins or catalyst level. The ratios can vary from 1:1 to 400:1 according to the resin in question. The ratio is usually varied by sliding an upper or lower pivot point on a slave arm [3], this to vary the stroke length for a piston pump or the rotational speed of a gear pump. It is also possible to modify the ratio via a variable speed motor according to the type of pump used. However, for the piston pump it is always possible to physically alter the dosage by simply changing the cylinder.

Mixers:

Static mixers are the type most frequently employed in RTM since they offer many advantages, such as;

- simplicity
- no moving parts
- ease of cleaning after each injection
- very little maintenance.

They are available in many different lengths and diameters according to the flow and viscosity of the fluid to be mixed [4].

Heating:

Pre-heating of the resin lowers viscosity, accelerates injection time and reduces hardening time for the part. Both resin and catalyst must be kept at the same temperature throughout the entire system, therefore making it necessary to heat the tanks, pumps, pipes and injection gun. As well, recirculation loops are often used. Temperature should be controlled by thermocouples installed throughout the system.

Reservoirs:

The size of reservoirs (or tanks) is determined according to the application. They must be heatable, equipped with a pneumatic agitator and when using the VARI process, be under vacuum.

Controls:

Apparatus such as flowmeters, pressure transducers and thermocouples are often employed to register and control critical parameters such as the resin/catalyst ratio, resin temperature and speed, and injection pressure. Upper and lower limit alarm systems are frequently used as well.

4.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS:

There exist a great variety of injection machines and it is difficult to find one machine that satisfies all applications. However, here is a list of desirable characteristics [2] for the selection of an injection machine;

- a. Precise and constant dosage with ratio capability from 1:1 to 400:1
- b. Positive displacement pumps with an accuracy of $\pm 1\%$
- c. Static mixer
- d. Uniform heating throughout the system (including a recirculation loop), permitting temperatures up to 100 to 120°C
- e. Controlled and adjustable flow
- f. Pressure capability up to 3,000KPa
- g. Simple construction, resistant to corrosion
- h. Capability to degas the resin and hardener
- i. Minimal material loss.

References

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TABLE 1 - RTM RESINS [2]

	Polyester	Vinylester	Phenolic	Epoxy	B.M.I.
Hardener (%)	0.5 - 2.5	0.5 - 2.5	2.0 - 8.0	10 - 100	N/A
Viscosity (CPS)					
Resin	100 - 300	100 - 300	500 - 700	100 - 300	500 - 2000
Hardener	50 - Paste	50 - Paste	50 -	50 - 1000	N/A
Process temperature (°C)	20 - 80	20 - 80	20 - 100	20 - 150	100 - 180
Work life (min.)	4 - 20	4 - 20	10	1 - 16 (hrs)	4 - 16 (hrs)

TABLE 2. - PUMP USED IN R.T.M.

PNEUMATIC					
Pumps	Pressure pot	Single acting pump	Double acting pump	Gears	Continual Displacement Pistons
TYPES	Pressure	Pressure	Pressure	Flow/pressure	Flow/pressure
Flow (Q) vs time (t)	Q t	Q t	Q t	Q t	Q t
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low cost - simple - easy clean up - metering and quick evaluation of all resins - direct pressure control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - simple - ease of maintenance - ease to automate - direct pressure control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - smooth, pulse-free flow of resin - constant turbulence and energy in the mixer - ease to automate - direct pressure control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - excellent flow control - unlimited volume per shot - variable flow rates/ratios by motor speed control - non-pulsed flow - excellent general control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no pulsations and pressure drops - injection can be controlled either by flow or pressure - accurate shot size - smooth filling of the tool - excellent general control
Inconveniences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no flow control - limited injection pressure - metering and mixing not automated - little process information - limited mold sizes - no evaluation of fast reacting resins - risk of fibre wash patterns and air entrapment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - indirect flow control - rapid pressure drop and loss of injection pressure - pulsating nature - pressure spikes can open or damage mold - less ratio versatility - risk of fibre wash patterns and air entrapment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - indirect flow control - pressure spikes can open or damage molds - more ball checks, seals, moving parts - more maintenance - less ratio versatility 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - limited viscosity acceptance levels - can be affected by back pressure - moving parts - no abrasive fillers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - less ratio versatility - limited shot size